

Equivalent conductance, viscosity and apparent molar volume studies of alkali metal propionates in propionic acid + ethanol mixture at 30°

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The equivalent conductance, density and viscosity of propionates of lithium, sodium and potassium in 50% (w/w) propionic acid + ethanol mixture have been measured at 35°. The conductance data have been analysed by using Fuoss-Kraus and Shedlovsky extrapolation methods and ion-pair association constants (λ_0 and K_a) determined. Reasonable agreement is found between the λ_0 and K_a values obtained by the two methods. The results are used to establish the nature of the ion-solvent interactions. The viscosity data have been analysed using the Jones-Dole equation. The activation parameters of viscous flow have been obtained which throw light on the mechanism of viscous flow. These electrolytes act as structure-promoters.

Even though studies on ion-solvent interactions in mixed solvents are quite extensive¹, such studies in binary solvents containing ethanol + nonaqueous ionizing cosolvent, specially where the anion of the ionizing cosolvent is the same as the anion of the salt are limited. This led the authors to undertake the title investigations, the results of which are presented here.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance values of the salts in 50% (w/w) propionic acid + ethanol mixture at 30° are presented in Table 1. These values are used to evaluate λ_0 graphically. A typical graph between λ and $C^{1/2}$ is presented in Fig. 1 for sodium propionate-solvent system. The data have been analysed by Fuoss-Kraus² and Shedlovsky³ equations to calculate the limiting molar conductance (λ_0) and ion-pair association constant (K_a), the details of which were given in our previous papers^{4,5}. The results

are presented in Table 2. The λ_0 and K_a values obtained by the two methods are in good agreement, and these values decreased in the order: $C_2H_5COOK > C_2H_5COONa > C_2H_5COOLi$. The trend indicates that smaller the cation, the greater is the solvation and consequently smaller are these values. A similar behaviour was observed earlier⁵ from the conductance study of metal formates in formic acid.

Table 1. Molar concentrations (C), densities (d), viscosities (η), equivalent conductances (λ), and apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) of alkali propionates in 50% (w/w) propionic acid-ethanol mixture at 30°

C g mol dm ⁻³	d g cm ⁻³	η Cp	λ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Lithium propionate (C ₂ H ₅ COOLi)				
0.0000	0.9052	1.436	—	—
0.0102	0.9055	1.443	30.10	13.15
0.0204	0.9065	1.454	27.95	18.24
0.0300	0.9070	1.462	24.37	20.80
0.0402	0.9074	1.470	20.43	26.14
0.0504	0.9083	1.487	18.92	25.61
0.0600	0.9085	1.495	17.20	28.72
0.0702	0.9089	1.500	14.74	30.39
0.0804	0.9092	1.510	13.44	32.67
0.0900	0.9105	1.522	12.42	34.12
0.1002	0.9112	1.539	10.32	35.21
Sodium propionate (C ₂ H ₅ COONa)				
0.0000	0.9052	1.436	—	—
0.0102	0.9060	1.446	43.50	15.64
0.0204	0.9067	1.455	38.70	32.20
0.0300	0.9071	1.468	34.00	37.33
0.0402	0.9075	1.481	30.10	42.62
0.0504	0.9081	1.489	25.80	43.62
0.0600	0.9086	1.497	22.93	44.29
0.0702	0.9089	1.506	20.89	48.17
0.0804	0.9092	1.524	19.35	51.08
0.0900	0.9098	1.525	16.53	51.29
0.1002	0.9103	1.534	14.52	53.98

Fig. 1. Plot of λ vs \sqrt{C} for sodium propionate in 50% (w/w) propionic acid-ethanol mixture at 30°.

Table-1 (contd.)

Potassium propionate (C ₂ H ₅ COOK)				
0.0000	0.9052	1.436	-	-
0.0102	0.9046	1.461	55.90	190.37
0.0204	0.9052	1.470	45.15	122.42
0.0300	0.9058	1.476	39.98	100.77
0.0402	0.9004	1.489	34.42	89.57
0.0504	0.9070	1.496	30.96	83.57
0.0600	0.9076	1.507	26.52	80.56
0.0702	0.9082	1.514	22.50	76.82
0.0804	0.9087	1.525	17.52	75.50
0.0900	0.9093	1.531	15.02	73.77
0.1002	0.9098	1.541	10.12	72.80

Table 2. Walden product ($\lambda_0\eta_0$), λ_0 and K_a values for propionates of lithium, sodium and potassium in 50% (w/w) propionic acid-ethanol mixture at 30°

Solute	Walden product ($\lambda_0\eta_0$)	Fuoss-Kraus		Shedlovsky	
		λ_0 Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	K_a dm^3 mol^{-1}	λ_0 Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	K_a dm^3 mol^{-1}
C ₂ H ₅ COOLi	57.43	43.48	74.86	45.46	87.83
C ₂ H ₅ COONa	87.55	62.50	68.35	66.70	77.85
C ₂ H ₅ COOK	109.11	83.30	123.51	90.90	138.00

The structural effect on the conductance of salts in solutions can be inferred through the comparison of Walden product values $\eta_0 \lambda_0$ which are given in Table 2. The values of Walden product give information regarding ion-solvent interactions in solutions. The variation in the Walden product as a function of the solvent is generally regarded as an index of specific ion-solvent interaction including structural effects. In the present study, as the measurements were made in only one solvent mixture, the variation in the values of $\eta_0 \lambda_0$ can be interpreted in terms of the solute-solvent interactions. In the present investigation, the anion of the three salts and anion of one of the solvents is the same, so the variation in the values of Walden product can be interpreted in terms of the ion-solvent interaction which is only due to the cations only. The data (Table 2) indicates that the magnitude of Walden product and, therefore, solute-solvent interactions in the solutions of three alkali propionates in propionic acid-ethanol mixtures show the following order : K-salt > Na-salt > Li-salt. These conclusions are in good agreement with those drawn from apparent molar volume studies. This suggests⁶ that the three salts are structure-makers in this solvent system. Similar conclusions were also drawn from the viscosity and apparent molar volume study of these salts as explained below.

Viscosity (η) and the density (d) data of these salts in 50% (w/w) PA-EtOH mixture at 30° and at different concentrations (C) are given in Table 1. The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) was calculated from density data using eq. (1),

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d_0} - \frac{1000(d - d_0)}{Cd_0} \quad (1)$$

where C is the molar concentration of the electrolyte, d the

density of the solution, d_0 the density of the solvent mixture and M_2 the molecular weight of the electrolyte. The ϕ_v values are also included in Table 1.

The apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v) vary linearly with C in conformity with the Masson's equation⁷,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^* C^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

The apparent molar volumes at infinite dilution ($\phi_v^0 = V_2^0$) and the slope (S_v^*) for the electrolytes are given in Table 3. The ϕ_v^0 values are positive and large indicating the presence of positive solute-solvent interactions. It is further observed that the ϕ_v^0 values follow the order : K-salt > Na-salt > Li-salt. Similar trend was reported by Desnoyers *et al.*⁸ in the case of partial molar volume of alkali metal halides in water-*t*-butanol mixtures. Smaller the size of the cation, greater is the ionic association or electrostriction and lesser is the ϕ_v^0 value.

Table 3. Values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* of Masson's equation for alkali propionates in 50% (w/w) propionic acid-ethanol mixture at 30°

Solute	ϕ_v^0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	S_v^* $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-3/2}$
C ₂ H ₅ COOLi	4.8	100.90
C ₂ H ₅ COONa	18.0	112.72
C ₂ H ₅ COOK	121.0	-0.33

S_v^* indicates the presence of ion-ion interaction in electrolytic solution. The S_v^* values for lithium propionate and sodium propionate are positive and that of potassium propionate is negative. Similar trend was reported with alkali metal chloride in water-methanol⁹ and water-*N*-methylacetamide mixtures¹⁰.

The viscosity data were analysed by means of the Jones-Doles equation¹¹,

$$(\eta/\eta_0) = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (3)$$

The values of A and B coefficients are obtained from the linear plots $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ vs \sqrt{C} and are given in Table 4. It is observed that A value for lithium propionate is negative whereas for propionates of sodium and potassium, the values are positive. Such negative values are not expected on the basis of Falkenhagen theory¹² and hence no significance is attached to these negative values as has been done by the other workers¹³. The small A values may however indicate that they contribute very little to absolute viscosities.

The B -values are positive and large indicating that the alkali metal propionates act as structure-makers in this mixed solvent system. The structure-making tendencies of the salts are in the order : Li-salt > Na salt > K salt. A similar trend was reported by Gill and Cheema¹⁴ in case of viscosities of perchlorates of lithium and sodium in propionic acid-ethanol mixture.

The viscosity data have also been analysed on the basis

of the transition state treatment of the relative viscosity of electrolytic solutions as suggested by Feakins *et al.*¹⁵. The *B*-parameter in terms of this theory is given by eq. (4),

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{V_1^0}{1000} \frac{\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}}{RT} \quad (4)$$

where (\bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 are the partial molar volumes of solvent and solute (at infinite dilution) respectively, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the contribution per mole of solute to the free energy of activation of viscous flow of the solution and $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ the free energy of activation per mole of the pure solvent and is given by eq. (5)¹⁶,

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln(\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (5)$$

where *h* is the Planck constant, *N* the Avogadro number and η_0 the viscosity of the solvent. Equation (4) is rewritten as

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + (RT/\bar{V}_1^0) [1000B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (6)$$

and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ values have been calculated from eq. (6). The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (Table 5) indicate that $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is practically constant in this solvent. This implies that $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is dependent mainly on *B*-coefficient and ($\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0$) term. The $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ values are positive and larger than $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ values, suggesting that the formation of the transition state is less favoured in the presence of these salts. This means that formation of the transition state is probably accompanied by cleavage and distortion of intermolecular bonds.

Table 4. Coefficient of Jones-Dole equation for viscosity coefficients of salts in 50% (w/w) propionic acid-ethanol mixture at 30°

Solute	<i>A</i>		<i>B</i>
	dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2}		
C ₂ H ₅ COOLi	-0.024		0.7333
C ₂ H ₅ COONa	+0.006		0.6667
C ₂ H ₅ COOK	+0.075		0.4933

Table 5. Values of molar free energy of activation for viscous flow of solution ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$) and of solvent ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$) at 30°

Solute	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$		$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$
	kcal mol ⁻¹		
C ₂ H ₅ COOLi	16.75		23.47
C ₂ H ₅ COONa	16.75		22.46
C ₂ H ₅ COOK	16.75		21.93

Experimental

Sodium propionate (Riedel, A.R.) was used as received. Lithium and potassium propionates were prepared and purified by the reported procedures¹⁷. The salts were dried and stored in vacuum desiccator.

Propionic acid (Fluka, purity >99.5%) was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, fractionally distilled and the fraction distilling between 139 and 141° was collected and redistilled in the presence of potassium permanganate, b.p. 140°/760 mm. Ethanol (A.R.) was treated with adequate quantity of preheated CaO, kept overnight and distilled.

The distillate was treated with metallic Na, refluxed, distilled and the middle fraction was collected for use.

The mixed solvent and the solutions were made by weight. A Biochem 808 conductivity meter (accuracy $\pm 0.2\%$) and a dip type conductance cell¹⁸ with smooth electrodes (since propionic acid is oxidised at platinized electrodes) were used. Density was measured using a double capillary pycnometer described earlier¹⁹. The precision in density determinations was within ± 2 parts in 10^4 which resulted in an uncertainty of 0.1 to 1.0 cm³ mol⁻¹ in ϕ_v values. Viscosity was measured using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer with a flow time of 302 s for water at 30°. The time of efflux was correct to ± 0.1 s. The precision of temperature control was $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Kinetic energy correction was not applied since the flow times were sufficiently large.

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